

‘An Analysis of Effects of Teacher’s Satisfaction on student ‘Satisfaction’

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Abstract:

The main objective of this study is to investigate the Impact of Teacher’s Satisfaction on Student’s Satisfaction of in Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur main campus and Shikarpur Campus. Data was collected through primary source for which both qualitative and quantitative methods are used. Interview guide for teacher’s satisfaction and student’s satisfaction was used as well as survey questionnaire used of both variables. Participants in this study were teachers and students of Shah Abdul Latif University main campus and Shikarpur Campus. Before data collection validity and reliability of questionnaires and interview guides were measured. 60% were male respondents. Further collected data was put into NVIVO 10 for analysis; Thus results conclude that there is a strong connection between teacher satisfaction and employee satisfaction. A satisfied teacher can produce qualitative, groomed, and productive human resources for various organizations, society and country as well.

Keywords: Satisfaction, Teacher’s Satisfaction, Student’s Satisfaction, Motivation.

Introduction

Teachers are the one of the most important ingredient and factor that affects an educational institute’s performance in today’s competitive environment. These are the only teachers who are responsible to satisfy the key customers of a University in the shape of the qualitative, productive, confidential, successful human resources. It has been seen that the satisfied teachers can produce highly qualified and satisfied students. As the teachers are ingredients for Universities to provide service quality to the customers (students) as well these teachers are considered to be as the source of committed, qualified, skilled human resources for various organizations in job market.

Today, higher Educational Institutes are considering themselves as the part of competitive environment among the service provider organizations. There are various public and private institutes are striving to capture the large market share in the shape of rankings. In the rapidly changing marketplace and various advancements in various fields of education, the universities are trying to be more proactive to satisfy the needs of the students.(Eyck, R., Tews, M., & Ballester, J. M., 2009).

On the other hand not only satisfied teachers are responsible for the student’s satisfaction but the highly qualified, trained, committed teachers are the source of satisfaction of the students, so we can say that the Universities have to keep meritocracy while recruiting the academic staff. In this regard universities administration has to formulate and implement the academic strategies that can satisfy their customers (students) at any cost, through this universities not only satisfy the students but also retain the students.(Helgesen, Ø., & Nettet, E, 2007).

Literature Review

Teacher’s Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is defined by various authors in various ways but unfortunately there is no prescribed definition of job satisfaction is considered. Some researchers connect it motivation but in real sense the motivation is a source of job satisfaction.Behaviour of employees towards the job in the sense of likeness and dislikes is called job satisfaction. (Spector, P. E. , 1997).

Furthermore job satisfaction is now become very challengeable for the organizations and by the employees. Job satisfaction is combination of self-reputation, self-respect, self-rule and the self-development at work place. (Bogler, R, 2001).

Teacher’s job satisfaction is not a big issue it is only interconnectivity among the teacher and his or her activities performed to deliver the knowledge backed by intellectuality, collaboration with students, parents, and colleges supported by the organizational environment.(Zembylas, M., & Papanastasiou, E. , 2004).

According to researcher in this article that job satisfaction is basic term to perform any job. As it is always observed that job satisfaction influences the job performance, hence we can say that job performance can direct impacted by job satisfaction. We can also say that job satisfaction is directly proportional to job performance. Furthermore author suggests those employees are very deeply attached to satisfaction of job, as their behaviour, attitude, and their perception level is also being affected by motivation.

Surroundings can also be affected if there is low level of job satisfaction. Furthermore researcher view that satisfaction can be influenced by the attitude of employee, if attitude is negative, its impact will be negative, if it is positive than satisfaction will be in positive points. Author also says about the likeness of employee also can impact the job satisfaction.(Pool, S. , 1997)

Although there is lot of literature available on job satisfaction in many areas of studies. Majority job satisfaction studies are conducted to know the employees satisfaction for the industrial organizations because the satisfied employees are considered as the pioneers of innovation, productivity and quality in work performance. The researcher emphasized that there is very few literature available to measure the employee satisfaction in the educational institutes up to some extent studies conducted on primary and secondary schools education but still there is huge gap to conduct the study on teacher's satisfaction of a university. (Oshagbemi, T. , 2003)

According to Meyer and Evans (2003), their interior inspiration and the actual position they contribute to the characteristics of the teaching profession (such as autonomy, motivation, career development, and flexibility) balance the multiple requirements, the durable compressions, and the poor financial rewards. In general context there are mainly two major factors that may affect the Teacher's satisfaction such as internal factors and the external factors. Internal factors from the side of administration and the external actors from the society side. A satisfied teacher is one who always want appreciated, motivated, belongingness with students as well as fellow teachers, recognition, professional growth in higher education context. Internally administration affect the teacher's satisfaction through rough work load assigned, non-meritorious policies in promotions, limited culture of relationship management with the students and other fellows. As it is natural phenomenon that the every individual want recognition, respect in the society so the society and sometimes political actors may also affect the teacher's satisfaction. On the other hand the teacher's seems to be less satisfied with the low compensation, less growth opportunities, and also work environment.(Ambrose, S., Huston, T., & Norman, M. , 2005)

Various studies are conducted to know the teacher's job satisfaction by various dimensions, easy in work load, work it –self, pay and compensations, qualitative supervision in positive manner, organizational motivation, and organizational commitment for the faculty development in research and academic area enhance the teacher's contributions towards the satisfaction. They have argued that the teacher's job

satisfaction directly impacts on the student's satisfaction as well as on the organizational overall performance, organization's policies, and initiatives, academic and administrative characteristics.(Malik Ehsan Muhammad, Vol. 5, No. 6; June 2010)

Student's Satisfaction

A simple definition of satisfaction "a person's feelings of pleasure that results from comparing a product's perceived performance or outcome to their expectations". So we can say that if the performance of product meets the expectations of a customer results in the satisfied customer. As we know that the students are considered to be as the customers of educational institutes so these customers can only be satisfied from the services delivered by higher education institutes. These are the valued services delivered by Higher Educational Institutions to the student's results in the successful and bright professional life of the students.(Kotler, P., Lane, K. K., Koshy, A., & Jha, M, 2009).

Student's satisfaction is measured on the basis of quality education provided by higher Educational Institutes because the Higher Educational Institutes are considered as the responsible for the overall development of a student's development practically and professionally. HEIs are the ladders for students to move towards the professional life so it is very critical situation for a HEI to provide quality education, and it is only possible form the satisfied and committed faculty and other administrative human resources. These are the today's customers can become tomorrow's personnel resources of the organization. Satisfied students are the signs of academic excellence of any HEI. So the satisfied students are the source of attracting more customers through word-of-mouth communication. Satisfied students can be used as entity to promote your service brands as well. (Alves, H. & Raposo M , 2010)

The academic and administrative performance are the key determinants of student's motivation. Universities can use the quality education as strategic tool to motivate the students through satisfied teachers for the betterment of educational excellence.(Ahmed, I., Nawaz, M. M., Ahmad, Z., Ahmad, Z., Shaukat, M. Z., Usman, A., Wasim-ulRehman & Ahmed, N., 2010).

According to Mavondo and Zaman (2000), academic status of the institution can be measured by quality of academic staff and the provision of market oriented facilities, extra co-curricular inputs for the student's mental development. The researcher indicated that satisfied students provide positive word of mouth and endorse future students to the institution at which they are studied. Student's Satisfaction also seems as the intended performance which results in one's

gratification. Thus student's satisfaction causes the validity and legitimacy to the system belongingness. So the satisfied students can be the signs of quality and prosperity for an HEI. These are the only students that becomes the successful brands of the university.

Research Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to analysis the effects of teacher's satisfaction on the student's satisfaction of the Shah Abdul Latif University main campus and Shikarpur Campus.

My first objective is to investigate the job satisfaction of teachers of Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur and its campus. In this regard certain factors such as demographic, workload, motivational, compensational relating to teacher's job satisfaction is taken under this study. Second objective of this study is to investigate the effects of teacher's satisfaction on the student's satisfaction. In this connection how students perceive the teacher's performance are explored.

Hypothesis

H1: Teacher's Satisfaction has directly impact on the student's satisfaction.

H2: Teacher's dissatisfaction has negative impact on the student's satisfaction

Research Model

Conceptual Model of the Study

Methodology

For conducting this research study both qualitative and quantitative methods are used to collect the data from students and teachers of Shah Abdul Latif University main campus and Shikarpur Campus. For collecting qualitative data 18 interviews were conducted from faculty members and students respectively. Interview questionnaire of teachers consist of 21 questions and interview questionnaire of students consist of 12 questions, normally 20 to 30 minutes were consumed to conduct an interview. For collecting quantitative data a 5-point Likert-scale survey questionnaire was formulated. In this regard 20 questionnaires were filled by teachers and students. Both interview questionnaire and Survey questionnaires further classified into different factors relating to both teachers and student's satisfaction.

Results and Discussion

Further collected data was analysed through NVIVO software as to know the accuracy of data and to know the effects of teacher's satisfaction on the student's satisfaction. Furthermore in NVIVO Software all the conducted interviews and survey data is inputted by preparing parent nodes and their respective child nodes as 1. Compensation along with its child nodes Intangible Rewards and Tangible Rewards, 2. Motivation including child nodes Employer Preferences and Work Environment, 3. Satisfaction including child node Teacher Satisfaction, 4. Student Satisfaction including child nodes Teacher's Methods and Teacher's Personality Traits and 5. Workload including child nodes Work Description and Work Itself. Demographic information is inputted in Node Classification and Matrix Coding Query, Word Text Query and Text Query were applied to get correlated results, results are shown in tables and diagrams as under.

Teacher Satisfaction

1. Compensation

Variable	A: Person Age Group= 20-30	B: Person Age Group= 30-40	C: Person Age Group= 40-50
1: Intangible Rewards	0%	100%	0%
2: Tangible	0%	100%	0%

2. Motivation

Variable	A: Person Age Group= 20-30	B: Person Age Group= 30-40	C: Person Age Group= 40-50
1: Employer Preferences	32.81%	34.37%	32.81%
2: Work Environment	32.81%	34.37%	32.81%

3. Satisfaction

Variable	A: Person Age Group= 20-30	B: Person Age Group= 30-40	C: Person Age Group= 40-50
1: Job Satisfaction	32.86%	34.28%	32.86%
2: Teacher Satisfaction	32.86%	34.28%	32.86%

4. Student's Satisfaction

Variable	A: Person Age Group= 20-30	B: Person Age Group= 30-40	C: Person Age Group= 40-50
1: Teacher Methods	32.86%	34.28%	32.86%
2: Teacher Personality Traits	32.86%	34.28%	32.86%

5. Workload

Variable	A: Person Age Group= 20-30	B: Person Age Group= 30-40	C: Person Age Group= 40-50
1: Work Description	32.81%	34.37%	32.81%
2: Work Itself	32.81%	34.37%	32.81%

Conclusions

The main objective of this study is to investigate the Impact of Teacher's Satisfaction on Student's Satisfaction of in Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur Mir's main campus and Shikarpur Campus. Data was collected through primary source for which both qualitative and quantitative methods are used. Interview guide for teacher's satisfaction and student's satisfaction was used as well as survey questionnaire used of both variables. Participants in this study were teachers and students of Shah Abdul Latif University main campus and Shikarpur Campus. Before data collection validity and reliability of questionnaires and interview guides were measured. 60% were male respondents. Further collected data was put into NVIVO 10 for analysis; Thus results conclude that there is a strong connection between teacher satisfaction and student's satisfaction. This study concludes that the other than work environment. A satisfied teacher can produce qualitative, groomed, and productive human resources for various organizations, society and country as well.

Appendix

Diagram#1. Matrix Coding Query

1. Compensation

2. Motivation

3. Satisfaction

4. Workload

5. Student Satisfaction

Diagram#4

Word Frequency Query Tree

Diagram#5

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